

Panagia Akatamachetos (Porta Panagia)

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The monastery of Porta Panagia was constructed by John I Doukas, the ruler of Thessaly (r. 1268-1289) in 1283. John I Doukas was the illegitimate son of Michael II Komnenos Doukas, the ruler of the Despotate of Epiros (r. 1230-1266/68). He was the half-brother of Nikephoros, the successor of Michael II. Porta Panagia stands in Pyli, a village in the vicinity of Trikala. Pyli, which means gate in Greek, marks the entry to a passage in the Pindus mountain range. The other end of the passage terminates at the monastery of Kato Panagia in Arta, which was built by John's father Michael II in ca. 1250. Halfway through this pass, in the village of Vourgareli at Tzoumerka, also stands the Red Church (Panagia of Vellas), which was constructed in the late thirteenth century. Primary sources mentioning Porta Panagia are a chrysobull by Andronikos III Palaiologos in 1331, a sworn letter by Michael Gabrielopoulos in 1342, and a synodical letter dated 1382. The initial plan of the church was that of a three-aisled basilica. Of interest is that the church contains the arcosolium of its founder, John I Doukas, and a painting depicting him as a monk above it. The church is also known for its two large mosaic icons flanking the templon screen. The mosaic icons depict the Virgin standing and holding the Christ child and Christ standing.

Date Range: 1283 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Pyli, Thessaly

Region tags: Greece

Pyli in Thessaly, near Trikala

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: A. Orlandos, “Η Πόρτα-Παναγιά της Θεσσαλίας,” *ABME* 1 (1935), 5-40; S. Mamaloukos, “Η Χρονολόγηση του καθολικού της Πόρτα-Παναγιάς,” in *Η Υπάτη στην εκκλησιαστική ιστορία, την εκκλησιαστική τέχνη και τον ελλαδικό μοναχισμό*. Πρακτικά, Υπάτη 8-10 Μαΐου 2009, Athens 2011, 463-479
- Source 2: A. Orlandos, “The Chronology of the Exonarthex of the Porta-Panagia in Thessaly,” I. Stevović (ed.), *Σύμμεικτα*. Collection of Papers Dedicated to the 40th Anniversary of the Institute for Art history, Belgrade 2012, 237-250
- Source 3: A. Tsitouridou, “Les fresques du XIIe siècle dans l’église de la Porta-Panaghia en Thessalie,” in *Actes du XVe Congrès International d’Études Byzantines*, Athènes-Septembre 1976, 2, Athens 1981, 863-878.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Other [specify]: river and near an entry to a mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Three-aisled basilica with a cross roof

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Burned and earthquake

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: natural disaster

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: dedicated to the Virgin

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Virgin

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: local ruler

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: Just the sebastokrator/ruler

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: clay, stone, plaster, brick

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster, brick, stone

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Notes: just templon screen, columns

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: arcosolium of founder

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: N/A

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Often. Liturgical rituals and celebrations of the Virgin

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– I don't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– I don't know

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Panagia Akatamachetos (Porta Panagia), Orlandos, Anastasios. “Η Πόρτα-παναγιά Της Θεσσαλίας”. ABME, 1935.

Reference: Panagia Akatamachetos (Porta Panagia), Mamaloukos, Stavros. “Η Χρονολόγηση Του Καθολικού Της Πόρτα-παναγιάς”. Athens: Ιερά Μητρόπολη Φθιώτιδος, 2011.

Reference: Panagia Akatamachetos (Porta Panagia), Mamaloukos, Stavros. The Chronology of the Exonarthex of the Porta-panagia in Thessaly. 2012: Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, n.d..

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